

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

How German farmers perceive the soil quality on their farms and which indicators they use

Farmers' perceptions of soil quality are of high importance in the development of more sustainable farming practices. The farmer survey implemented in SoildiverAgro identified relevant agri-environmental problems in the present production as well as the most effective farming practices to face these problems. The survey data was collected from six different regions of Europe. In Germany 200 farmers provided survey answers. Of them 91% were conventional farmers and 9% organic. The survey assessed the indicators utilized by farmers to evaluate soil quality. Among all the indicators, those most commonly employed included soil structure (81% of farmers used), pH

levels (69%), and water holding capacity (61%). In Germany, also organic matter content emerged as a frequently applied indicator (46%). Of farmers 44% followed the soil compaction regularly. Less used indicators were number of earth worms. Farmers were asked about how they perceived the current average soil quality on their farms using the indicators they employed for evaluation. Soil quality was generally regarded as rather good, as 50% of respondents selecting this option, while 40% evaluated it as neither good nor bad. Of farmers 5% considered the soil quality as very good and 1% as very bad.

1. Adapted soil cultivation in a mixed agricultural farm in the German low mountain range. © BLE/Thomas Stephan

KEYWORDS

Soil quality, sustainable land use, indicators

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